

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

INCREASING RESERVOIR PRODUCTIVITY BY EXPOSURE TO ACID COMPOSITIONS AT THE KARAZHANBAS OIL FIELD

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Abstract

The main reason for the low productivity of wells, along with poor natural permeability of the formation and poor-quality perforation, is a decrease in the permeability of the bottomhole zone of the formation.

The bottomhole formation zone is the area of the formation around the borehole, which is most intensively affected by various processes accompanying the construction of the well and its subsequent environment and disrupting the initial equilibrium mechanical and physico-chemical state of the formation.

Drilling itself makes a change in the distribution of internal stresses in the surrounding rock face. A decrease in well productivity during drilling also occurs as a result of penetration of the solution or its filtrate into the bottom-hole zone of the formation. When the filtrate interacts with stratified mineralized water, insoluble salts may form and precipitate, clay cement swells and clogging of persistent emulsions, and a decrease in the phase permeability of wells. There may not be high-quality perforation due to the use of low-power perforators, especially in deep wells, where the charge explosion emulsion is absorbed by the energy of high hydrostatic pressures.

A decrease in the permeability of the bottomhole formation zone occurs during the operation of wells, accompanied by a violation of the thermobaric equilibrium in the reservoir system and the release of free gas, paraffin and asphalt-resinous substances from the oil, clogging the steam space of the reservoir.

Keywords: research, well, steady-state filtration modes, formation, flow rate, oilfield.

Research. The Karazhanbas field is located in the northwestern part of the Buzachi peninsula of the Mangystau region of the Republic of Kazakhstan, and is adjacent to the eastern shore of the Caspian Sea. From this oil field to the nearest city of Aktau) about 210 km. The length of the field from east to west is 30 km, the width from south to north is 6 km, the area is about 180 km². The surface of this area is a salt and silk threshold, the vehicle passes very difficult. Some of it is a sand dome and discovered old rocks.

Mangystau region is known for the fact that about a quarter of the recoverable reserves of raw materials are concentrated on its territory. The deposits are mainly due to their complex geological structure, therefore, the exploitation of these fields does not make it possible to extract oil reserves in full volumes, but only 5-7%.

The tectonic structure of this region is described in the works of S.N.Alekseychik, then it is covered in more detail in the publications of B.F.Dyakov, A.I.Dimakov, G.V.Shvedov, the geological structure of local uplifts in the center of the Buzachinsky arch is detailed according to the indicators of structural prospecting drilling (A.M.Nurmanov, H.J.Uzbekgaliev, etc.). Problems of the structural position The Paleozoic and Triassic complexes are interpreted in the works of Vasiliev, Milnichuk, Charygin, etc. In the works of Volozh, Votzalevsky,

Lipatova, the internal structure of the pre-Jurassic complex of the Buzachi peninsula is studied.

The process of development and formation of the Karazhanbassky deposit directly depends on the features of the paleotectonic structure of the Buzachinsky arch, located at the junction of the East European and Central Eurasian platforms. [1-2].

Intensive contamination of the bottom-hole zone of the formation is also noted as a result of the penetration of working fluids during various repair work in wells. The intake capacity of injection wells deteriorates due to blockage of the pore space with petroleum products contained in the injected water. As a result of the penetration of such processes, the filtration resistance of liquid and gas increases, well flow rates decrease and there is a need for artificial impact on the bottom-hole zone of the formation in order to increase the productivity of wells and improve their hydrodynamic connection with the formation.

Limestone and dolomite dissolve in hydrochloric acid: calcium chloride, magnesium chloride, salts are acid carriers well soluble in water, and are easily removed from the formation. Carbon dioxide is also easily removed from wells, and at pressures above 7.6 MPa, they dissolve in the same water. The optimal concentration of hydrochloric acid in the solution is assumed to be 10-16%. The use of acid with a low concentration (less than 10%) causes the need to pour a large amount of water into the reservoir, as a result of

which the process of well development after acid treatment may be complicated

Hydrochloric acid treatment can be used in wells exploiting carbonate, fractured-pore formations of any thickness. The objects of treatment may be poorly developed (after drilling or major repairs) wells and wells that significantly reduced the flow rate during operation. Treatments are assigned to determine the current and potential productivity coefficients.

To carry out hydrochloric acid treatment of injection wells, wells should be selected that must meet the following requirements:

- the permeability of the exposed layers is 300-600 mdarsi and higher; I
- the well capacity is more than 500 m / day and, with time, decreases to 100 m / day and lower;
- the well should pour out;
- the wellhead fittings and the service column must be sealed [1-4].

The effectiveness of salt treatment of wells depends on the concentration of acid, its amount, pressure during processing, temperature at the bottom, the nature of rocks and other factors. For acid treatments, the volume and concentration of the acid solution are planned individually for each field and each well, since it is difficult to accurately calculate these parameters. The limit values of these parameters are usually as follows: volume – 0.4–1.5 m³ per 1 m of the treated reservoir capacity; concentration of 12-16% HCl with a decrease in some cases to 8% and an increase to 20%.

The working solution of HCl content at the place of its storage (acid base) or directly at the well before its treatment.

Since hydrochloric acid coming from factories can have different concentrations, it is necessary to calculate exactly how much water and acid must be

mixed to obtain a solution of the specified concentration and volume.

The amount of commercial acid 1" in volume units required to obtain 1 m³ of a working solution of a given concentration is calculated using the following formula:

$$V_m = \frac{1}{1 - \frac{\rho_m - \rho_s}{\rho_s - 1000}} = \frac{\rho_s - 1000}{\rho_m - 1000} \quad (1)$$

or for any number of cubic meters

$$V_m = n \frac{\rho_s - 1000}{\rho_m - 1000} \quad (2)$$

where is the volume of commercial acid, is the density of commercial acid, kg / m; is the specified density of the finished solution, kg / m; is taken based on the specified percentage of HCl in the working solution.

To prepare a solution of a given concentration of Cl, commercial acid is diluted in containers, the volume of which is strictly calibrated.

According to the calculation, water is poured into the container, then concentrated commercial acid is poured and all necessary additives (inhibitors, surfactants, etc.) are added in the summer.

Additives of inhibitor reagents, surfactants are usually so insignificant that corrections for the volumes of these reagents are not introduced.

The flow rate at well 1771 before the SCO was 3.4 t/day, after the SCO – 3.9 t/ day. The duration of the technological effect was 174 days. Additional production of 87 tons

The flow rate at well 2249 before the SCO was 1.1 t/day, after the SCO – 1.6 t/ day. The duration of the technological effect was 196 days. Additional production of 98 tons

Table 1.

The effectiveness of the SCO

№ скв	Дата проведения	Дебит нефти, т/сут		Продолжительность эффекта, сут	Дополнительная добыча, т
		До ремонта	После ремонта		
1771	07.06.21	3,4	3,9	174	87
2249	22.01. 21	1,1	1,6	196	98
12314	25.02. 21	5,1	5,2	210	21
12523	15.07. 21	5,4	5,7	153	45,9
12899	12.08. 21	1,1	2,2	149	163,9
13512	13.03. 21	1,1	1,5	183	73,2
13813	12.04. 21	4,9	6,5	171	273,6
14015	29.09. 21	1,5	2,2	160	112
14175	23.05. 21	2,0	2,4	189	75,6
14202	17.04. 21	0,9	1,2	229	68,7
Среднее значение				181,4	101,9

Well treatment with hydrochloric acid has found the most widespread use due to its comparative simplicity, low cost and often favorable reservoir conditions for its use.

Limestone, dolomite, or carbonate cementing agents are often present in various quantities in oily

rocks. Hydrochloric acid dissolves such rocks well, while the following main reactions occur.

When exposed to limestone:

When exposed to dolomite:

Calcium chloride (CaCl_2) and magnesium chloride (MgCl_2) are salts that are highly soluble in the carrier water of the acid formed as a result of the reaction. Carbon dioxide (CO_2) is also easily removed from the well, or at an appropriate pressure (over 7.6 MPa) it dissolves in the same water.

It is known that 1 liter of a 15% acid solution contains 161.2 g of pure HCL. Therefore, it will take 4.53 liters of solution to dissolve 1 kg of limestone [2-5].

Calculation of borehole treatment with hydrochloric acid. Initial data:

Depth $H = 3800$ m

The uncovered effective capacity of the carbonate reservoir $h = 25$ m

The inner diameter of the well $D = 0.154$ m

Tubing diameter $d = 0.05$ m

Determination of the required amount of chemicals.

For the given conditions, we assume an acid concentration of 8%. With an average consumption rate of 1.2 m^3 of this acid per 1 m of the treatment interval, the total volume of hydrochloric acid will be $1.2 \text{ m} \times 25 = 30 \text{ m}^3$.

Calculation of the amount of chemicals and water.

The preparation of 6 m^3 of 8% hydrochloric acid solution requires 1840 kg of 27.5% HCl and 4.38 m^3 of water, and 30 m^3 of 8% hydrochloric acid solution requires concentrated HCl:

$$W_k = \frac{1840}{6} \cdot 30 = 9200 \text{ кг} \quad (2.2)$$

and water:

$$V = \frac{4,38}{6} \cdot 30 = 21,9 \text{ m}^3 \quad (3)$$

The amount of concentrated commercial hydrochloric acid for a 10% hydrochloric acid solution can also be found by the formula:

$$W_k = \frac{AxxW(B \quad z)}{Bz(A \quad x)} \quad (4)$$

where $A = 214$ and $B = 226$ are numerical coefficients for an acid of 8% concentration; x is the 8% concentration of hydrochloric acid solution; z is the 27.5% concentration of commercial acid; $B = 30 \text{ m}^3$ is the volume of the acid solution.

Therefore,

$$W_k = \frac{214 \cdot 8 \cdot 30 \cdot (226 \quad 27,5)}{226 \cdot 27,5 \cdot (214 \quad 8)} = 7,96 \text{ m}^3$$

we accept $B_k = 8 \text{ m}^3$.

We take unicol U-2 as an inhibitor. The required amount of unicol is determined by the formula:

$$Q = \frac{74bxW}{A \quad x} \quad (5)$$

where b is the percentage of the unicol additive to hydrochloric acid (for unicol U-2, 5% by volume of the amount of concentrated acid is taken, for unicol M-N – 1% and for U-K – 0.3%); x is the 8% concentration of hydrochloric acid solution; $B = 30 \text{ m}^3$ is the volume of acid solution; A is a numerical coefficient assumed to be equal to 214 for an 8% acid concentration.

Therefore,

$$Q = \frac{74 \cdot 5 \cdot 8 \cdot 30}{214 - 8} = 431 \text{ л}$$

Against the precipitation of the hydrochloric acid solution of the iron salts contained in it, add acetic acid in the amount of:

$$Q_{y.k.} = \frac{1000bW}{C}, \quad (6)$$

where b is the percentage of acetic acid additive to the volume of the solution; $B = 30 \text{ m}^3$ is the volume of hydrochloric acid solution; C is the concentration of acetic acid (we take 80%).

Therefore,

$$Q_{y.k.} = \frac{1000 \cdot 1,5 \cdot 30}{80} = 562,5 \text{ л},$$

To dissolve the siliceous compounds contained in the rock and prevent their precipitation in the form of a gel of silicic acid, add hydrofluoric acid to hydrochloric acid in the amount of:

$$Q_{n.k.} = \frac{1000bW}{m}, \quad (7)$$

$$Q_{n.k.} = \frac{1000 \cdot 1 \cdot 30}{60} = 500 \text{ л},$$

where b is the percentage of hydrofluoric acid additive to the volume of the solution (1%); $B = 30 \text{ m}^3$ is the volume of hydrochloric acid solution; m is the concentration of commercial hydrofluoric acid as a percentage of HF content (usually $m = 60\%$). Therefore

Commercial hydrochloric acid of the second grade contains an admixture of sulfuric acid in an amount of up to 0.6%, which, after its reaction with calcium carbonate, forms gypsum, which falls out in the form of crystals clogging the pores of the formation.

Against gypsum precipitation, add barium chloride to hydrochloric acid in the amount of

$$Q_{xx.} = 21,3W \left(\frac{ax}{z} - 0,02 \right), \quad (8)$$

where $B = 30 \text{ m}^3$ is the volume of hydrochloric acid solution; $a = 0.6\%$ is the SO_3 content in commercial hydrochloric acid; x is the 8% concentration of hydrochloric acid solution; $z = 27.5\%$ is the concentration of commercial acid;

$$Q_{xx.} = 21,3 \cdot 30 \left(\frac{0,6 \cdot 8}{27,5} - 0,02 \right) = 98,75 \approx 100 \text{ кг}$$

or 25 liters at a density of 4.0 barium chloride.

As an intensifier to reduce surface tension, we use the drug DS (detergent Soviet), which is both an inhibitor and the most active reducing agent of the reaction rate of hydrochloric acid with rock. A large decrease in the reaction rate contributes to a deeper penetration of acid into the formation.

The required amount of DS is 1-1.5% of the volume of hydrochloric acid solution (we accept 1%). This gives

$$30 \text{ m}^3 \cdot 0.01 = 0.3 \text{ m}^3 \text{ or } 300 \text{ liters.}$$

The amount of water to prepare the accepted volume of hydrochloric acid solution:

$$V = B - B_k - \sum Q \text{ m}^3 \quad (9)$$

where B_K is the volume of hydrochloric acid solution; $B_K = 8 \text{ m}^3$ is the volume of concentrated commercial hydrochloric acid:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum Q &= 431 + 562,5 + 500 + 25 + 300 = 1818,50 \text{ л} \approx \\ &1,82 \text{ m}^3 \\ V &= 30 - 8 - 1,82 = 20,18 \text{ m}^3 \end{aligned}$$

To isolate the zumpf, we use a solution of calcium chloride with a density of 1.2.

The volume of 1 m of the borehole with an internal diameter of 0.154 m is 0.0186 m^3 (0.785×0.154^2), and the volume of 12 m of the sump will be 0.223 m^3 .

To obtain calcium chloride with a density of 1.2, according to the instructions, 540 kg of CaCl_2 and 0.66 m² of water of 1 m³ solution are required. To isolate everything, you need to take: CaCl_2 $540 \times 0.223 = 120.53 \text{ kg}$ and water $0.66 \times 0.223 = 0.15 \text{ m}^3$.

After preparing the hydrochloric acid solution, the obtained concentration of HCl solution is checked with a hydrometer, and if it does not correspond to the set one, water or concentrated acid is added to the solution

The amount of added water at HCl concentration > 8% is determined by the formula

$$q_B = \frac{(p_2 - p)W}{p - 1}, \quad (10)$$

The amount of hydrochloric acid added, if the HCl concentration is < 8%, is according to the formula

$$q_B = \frac{(p - p_1)W}{p_3 - p}, \quad (11)$$

Where q_B and q_k are the volumes of added water and concentrated acid in m³; B is the volume of hydrochloric acid solution of 8% concentration; p is the density of the solution of a given concentration; p_1 and p_2 are the density of the prepared solution of reduced and increased concentrations, respectively; p_3 is the density of concentrated hydrochloric acid

Conclusion. The main PZP method for wells with carbonate fractured – porous reservoirs is hydrochloric acid treatment. There are various ways of influencing hydrochloric acid on the carbonate formation (baths, simple acid treatments, deep-directed, intervertebral, etc.).

Most hydrochloric acid treatments can improve the permeability of the bottomhole formation zone.

Processing of zones remote from the borehole presents certain difficulties due to the inability to deliver hydrochloric acid to the depth of the formation. As a result of the high rate of acid reaction in the carbonate component of the formation, water is released in the bottomhole zone, which is pushed into the depth of the formation by another portion of acid.

When using most methods of treating the formation with hydrochloric acid, hydrochloric acid is absorbed by the drained zones of the formation, and non-working areas remain untreated. This explains the low efficiency of repeated hydrochloric acid treatments.

Currently, 76% of the total number of wells are producing in the northern part of the field (45 producing wells) and 14 wells are producing in its southern part.

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